

At a Glance

Acronym: GILL

Title: Gendered Innovation Living Lab

Call identifier: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-80

Total Budget: € 2,589,225

Project duration: 36 months

Start Date: 1st January 2023

Project Coordinator: ENoLL

The **GILL project** develops a **pan-European collaboration and learning hub** as a **one-stop-shop** for **tools, methods, and knowledge** to reduce gender barriers in innovation and entrepreneurship, by enabling the transformation of individual, team and educational practices.

Nurturing the environment and skills needed to support **Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship**, GILL contributes to the creation of a fairer **Open Innovation Ecosystem** (OIE).

Contact us

For **more information** on GILL project please contact at: info@gi-ll.eu

Project Coordinator

European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)

Consortium

The **GILL consortium** is formed by **17 project partners** from **10 European countries** which namely are **Belgium, France, Greece, Italy, Spain, Romania, Germany, Denmark, UK, Czech Republic**

Funded by the European Union

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This project is co-funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10049511]*

One-Stop-Shop Collaboration & Learning Hub for reducing Gender Barriers in Innovation and Entrepreneurship

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The challenge

According to EC research, Europe shows a strong **under-utilisation of female talent** and still reports a high disproportion in the representation of **women** and those from diverse and minority groups in innovation and **entrepreneurship activities** and outputs. Examples of such facts are the **high drop-out rate** of women at postgraduate level in STEM, the presence of **discriminatory practices** such as the **pay gap** observed between male and female employees, as well as **lower career progression**, and lastly the under-representation of women among **innovators** and **start-up entrepreneurs**.

What does GILL address?

Women in Europe, particularly those from diverse and minority groups in local societies, face significant barriers to equal participation in the fields of innovation and entrepreneurship.

GILL creates the Tools and Methods:

- ◆ **to change the culture** around innovation and entrepreneurship
- ◆ **to change the practice** (as a bottom-up approach which enables EU strategies and policies to be enacted)
- ◆ **to shape the environment** and develop the skills needed to support **Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE)** in the **Open Innovation Ecosystems (OIEs)**.

GILL Methodology & Pilots

By applying the **co-creation approach** and principles Of the **Living Labs** ecosystems, **along with** the user-centred design and citizen's science, GILL aims to fix the culture and practices by developing and testing **15 Action-Oriented Experimentations (pilots)** in **8 European Countries** i.e. *Italy, UK, Spain, Greece, Romania, Denmark, Germany, Czech Republic*

GILL co-creation of methods and tools is implemented through **two iteration cycles** to incorporate the feedback and evaluation results in **four participatory phases**:

The produced **results will be available** on a sustainable and easy-to-use platform.

Objectives

GILL focuses on:

- ◆ **enabling organisational** and cultural changes,
- ◆ **enhancing professional** development,
- ◆ **increasing the integration of gender** and diversity into product design, technologies, and innovation,
- ◆ **allowing gendered** educational practices.

all this within **3 application domains**:

- ◆ **Health** and resilience
- ◆ **Green** transition
- ◆ **Digital** transformation

Who benefits from GILL?

The educational and research sector gain knowledge and tools to allow gendered educational practices.

Civil society gains access to training to increase its power and influence on democratic and innovation processes.

Industry and the private sector benefits from tools to increase the integration of gender and diversity into product design, technologies, and innovation.

The government and public sector is offered with tools and recommendations for more gender-responsive policy-making.